

TOPS November Community Panel Quotes

Day One – Community Panel - General Remarks Quotes

Disha Sardana, Virginia Tech, Blacksburg

Original Quote:

“I was thinking like, I wish I had gone through this before starting my PhD or when I was transferring from my masters to PhD. Because like no one tells you how to share your data.”

Revised Version:

“I wish I had gone through this before starting my PhD or when I was transferring from my masters to PhD. Because no one tells you how to share your data.”

Day One – Community Panel OS101 Curriculum Review Quotes

Emily Faber, University of Maryland, Baltimore County

Original Quote:

"I'm a physicist, and I work in the earth science department. And I found myself being able to put myself in the shoes of anybody, even in astrophysics, or there was a biology example... The knowledge checks are fair, those are on target. The language is inclusive and inviting."

Revised Version:

"I'm a physicist, and I work in an Earth Science Department. The Open Science 101 curriculum is inclusive and inviting. As I completed each module, I found that I was able to better understand the work of others in different fields and disciplines, like astrophysics or biology. And I enjoyed that I was able to test myself on what I was learning through various knowledge check activities."

Junellie Gonzalez Quiles, Johns Hopkins University

Original Quote:

"But I thought I also got really excited as Emily said, like, I like read, and I was like, Oh, my God, like, I can't wait to apply this to my research and like to learn more."

Revised Version:

"Open science is exciting. As I worked my way through the open science content, I was amazed at all of the information I was learning. I can't wait to apply these important strategies, tools, and lessons to my research."

SherAaron Hurt, Director of Workshops and Training - The Carpentries

Original Quote:

"But we'll say one readability in the flow, and being able to comprehend that I love the language or, you know, what I'm reading. I never felt as though I didn't know or, you know, like, the tone or as I was reading, like, Oh, I understand that. It's almost like I'm reading a book or as if someone's talking to. So the tone is absolutely marvelous. The other thing, too, just from going from Module One to two, I love that it is very high level overview."

Revised Version:

"I truly enjoyed the readability and flow of NASA's Open Science 101 curriculum. The overall tone of the modules is inviting and marvelous. As a learner, you feel like you are reading a good book and learning from an informed instructor. I also really love that Modules One and Two provide learners a high-level overview of the importance of Open Science."

Brian Nosek, Founder of Center for Open Science

Original Quote:

"I've read lots of intros to open science over the years. And this one is by far the best, assuming no knowledge to gain, clarity and then especially on the two parts that are the most complex of this introduction, which is there multiple motivations for open science, democratizing access, inclusion, transparency, sharing rigor, manages to weave them together a narrative that makes sense. And there are multiple behaviors that code software or distraction data management, planning, all that stuff, and it's all it all makes sense. So navigating that complexity is really hard. It comes through in a way that it gives a reader would say Oh, I get it I understand it."

Revised Version:

"NASA's Open Science 101 curriculum offers the best opportunity for people to gain knowledge about the complexities and opportunities that exist with open science. There are multiple motivations for open science: democratizing access, inclusion, transparency, sharing, and rigor - this curriculum manages to weave these complex concepts together into a narrative that makes sense."

Original Quote:

"But we'll say one readability in the flow, and being able to comprehend that I love the language or, you know, what I'm reading. I never felt as though I didn't know or, you know, like, the tone or as I was reading, like, Oh, I understand that. It's almost like I'm reading a book or as if someone's talking to. So the tone is absolutely marvelous. The other thing, too, just from going from Module One to two, I love that it is very high level overview."

Revised Version:

“The readability in the flow and being able to comprehend it all is great. You know, what I'm reading. It's almost like I'm reading a book or as if someone's talking to you. The tone is absolutely marvelous.”

Day Two – Community Panel - General Remarks Quotes**Junellie Gonzalez Quiles, Johns Hopkins University****Original Quote:**

“My comment was about just like thinking about my own journey. And the challenges I face and the barriers I felt like I've had to deal with during my undergrad and PhD degrees is that a lot of the barriers that I've encountered were things I didn't even know I needed to know. So essentially, I'm thinking about what can we do even before we started attempting to think about open science. So for example, I share in the, in the chat that as I mentioned yesterday, one of the things that I didn't even know when I first started, you know, in this journey of becoming an astronomer is that I didn't even know coding was part of my job. And so identifying those things that people don't really realize, and like, you know, kids and the rising generation of scientists don't realize our part of the job is like so essential for us to be able to, like come in with a better understanding of what the job actually entails.”

Revised Version:

“Identifying the barriers that people don't even realize they have is essential in breaking them down for the next generation of scientists and it's our duty as scientists to do that. To identify these barriers, we first need to look at the wide range of skills that are needed for many careers in different fields and really think about how future scientists can not only learn about these much needed skills, but also acquire them to succeed in their careers.”

Original Quote:

“I think there's this mentality in academia where, you know, advisors are like, recruiting students with the mindset that they're lacking this experience, I have to give it to them. But rather move that framework and mindset from this person is lacking this experience, because either they came from another country or something, too, they have all of these skills, like other skills and experience, how can we work together? And how can we highlight and use those skills that they come from come with, to get to where they need to be in terms of their career, and I think that's just like a mindset thing that needs, I feel like would be very helpful, you know, moving the state of the field forward.”

Revised Version:

“There's a mindset in academia that advisors look for students to fill a gap when it comes to their research and is usually thought about as a lack of experience from the student that they will then acquire. Rather than approaching mentoring with this “lacking” mindset, advisors and mentors need to look at the rich set of experiences and skills they have already acquired in their careers and really think about what the mentee wants to accomplish in their careers and how they can use those experiences to

succeed. By doing so, we can shift to a mindset of thinking “what do they need and how can we work together to succeed” to create a culture change that is much needed in STEM.”

Brian Nosek, Founder of Center for Open Science

Original Quote:

“In those kind of like things, they may seem very simple. But as someone who doesn't know, that, like, you know, encountered those barriers, and that makes it extremely difficult, you know, if we don't know that we should know this, then it's just hard for us to get on the same footing. And, you know, and other students that come also from underrepresented backgrounds.”

Revised Version:

“Students from underrepresented backgrounds may not know what they don't know, and they may not be supported to overcome the current barriers they face.”

Original Quote:

One thing I would add is that design has to be for the individuals interest. And institutions sometimes framed or aims at a social level rather than as an individual level. So to give a concrete example, University of Virginia has aspirations, my institution aspirations to diversify the leadership of the institution, gender, and ethnicity, especially. So they've developed lots of programs to create greater diversity in leadership. My spouse is a senior seventh researcher. So she's an ideal target for the institution to say, let's elevate her to more senior leadership to the most somebody are. So they have programs like, come to this thing where you commit four hours of your week, every week to learn how to be a leader. And one of those four hour sessions is the art of saying no. And she said four hours every week to do this thing that is totally interfering with my actual success. And so the intention was great, let's diversify at the social level. And the implementation was ironic, in actually undermining the individuals that are participating by adding this burden to their time it wasn't actually like raising your capacity.”,

Revised Version:

“Not being inclusive and equitable with schedule or time requirements is also a social barrier to science and academia.”

James Colliander, 2i2c Co-Founder and Professor of Mathematics, UBC

APPROVED - JC prefers original quote over revision.

Original Quote:

“I think the underlying principle here is that there's really a human right to participate in science. But if you want to participate in astronomy, in 1950, you have to have access to place your eyeball on the eyepiece. And if you want to participate in scholarly reading, you have to have the right library card to be able to get into the library and get access to documents. But

we're at a change era now, because of the ubiquity of digital tools. So we can create different social structures to allow for a more fulfilled right to participate, you can look through a telescope via your computer. Now, you don't have to be at the telescope. And you can get access to the information in the library without having the Harvard Library card. So there are new opportunities to build structures that allow for people that previously were excluded to participate in new ways.”

Revised Version:

“We're in an era of change now with open science. So, we can create different social structures to allow for a more fulfilled right to participate. There are new opportunities to build structures that allow for people that previously were excluded to participate in new ways.

Additional Feedback/Post-Panel Quotes

Open Science 101 Curriculum

Pen-Yuan Hsing: On OS101 course: “I’ve seen several open science curricula over the years, and agree with the others that this is not only top tier material, but also is itself an exemplary demonstration of open science in action. Huge thanks to everyone who brought OS101 to life. 10/10 would recommend.”

General Feedback/Comments

Pen-Yuan Hsing: After another stimulating panel meeting, this time with inspiring student members, I feel stronger in my belief that: “Good science *is* open science. And in light of the urgent global challenges of today - from climate change, diseases, to how we govern ourselves - we *cannot afford* to do closed science. We simply don’t have the time!”

Open Science 101 Curriculum + general feedback

Malvika Sharan: “OS101 stands as a remarkable example of open science in practice. Developed on existing open science resources and infrastructure, the richness of the content is attributed to the involvement of diverse international contributors, all of whom are recognized and rewarded for their contributions. The high-quality, openly accessible course material showcases how open science significantly enhances research, fostering a collaborative spirit in knowledge production, access, dissemination, and reuse.”